

From Stage to Data : Ontologies for Performing Arts and Linked Open Data

Clarisse Bardiot, Bernard Jacquemin, Antonios Lagarias, Jeanne Fras, Nicolas Foucault, Jacob Hart, Alexandra Beraldin

The representation and interconnectivity of performing arts data pose significant challenges due to their inherent complexity. As part of the ERC-funded project *From Stage to Data, the Digital Turn of Contemporary Performing Arts Historiography* (STAGE), this study investigates the development of an ontology capable of ensuring interoperability between existing ontologies and databases, with a specific focus on the adoption of linked open data principles and the Linked Art ontology, which is built upon the CIDOC CRM framework. By addressing these challenges, the project aims to unify fragmented datasets, enhance the discoverability of performing arts data, and foster interdisciplinary research.

One of the most significant performing arts events in the world, with over 2.000 performances staged by companies from all over the world, the Avignon festival is central to this initiative. At the very center of contemporary performing arts life, it has become the “agora of European theatre” (Banu and Tackels 2005), gathering thousands of spectators and journalists each year, showing and revealing the essential artists after WWII, not only theatre but also dance, performance, circus: Mnouchkine, Brook, Wilson, Chéreau, Bausch, Ostermeier, Castellucci, Marthaler, De Kersmaecker, Rizzo, Cassiers, Forsythe, Cunningham, Nadj, The Living Theatre, Abramovic... One of the STAGE project’s objectives is the extraction of data from the festival’s theater programs – an essential source for the history of the performing arts – to highlight the interactions among thousands of individuals, the various forms of artistic and technical collaborations, and the evolution of creation contexts over time.

On the surface, theater programs may seem straightforward to transform into a database, with “obvious” categories such as play title, author, director, actors, and venue. However, these categories are not free of definitional problems, or simply anachronisms, particularly for functions linked to the performing arts professions, starting with that of director (Bardiot 2021). Transforming such data while preserving their semantic richness often requires making compromises that risk reducing their content. Furthermore, performances themselves are complex artistic objects: they involve numerous individuals in varying roles, may be staged on different dates, generate publications, photographs, or films, be reinterpreted by others, and exist in multiple states (e.g., works in progress). These challenges have hindered the development of a unified ontological model for describing performances, complicating interoperability between existing databases (Roussillon and Schuway 2020; Oort and Noordegraaf 2020; Bardiot 2021; Douguet 2024). The models underlying these databases are often poorly documented or unpublished, further limiting their utility.

Overview of Existing Models

Several models have been developed to structure and represent performing arts data, each with its strengths and limitations. We critically examines existing models such as FRBR, CIDOC CRM, and their adaptations, including FRBRoo (now LRMoo) and specialized frameworks like AusStage¹,

1 <https://www.ausstage.edu.au/pages/learn/data-models>

Linked Stage Graph², ECLAP and EDM³, Swiss Performing Arts (SPA)⁴, Pina Bausch Foundation and CapData Opéra⁵. FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records), for instance, was originally developed to structure bibliographic records but provides a foundation for adapting hierarchical models in the arts domain. CIDOC CRM, by contrast, focuses on event-based modeling, offering unparalleled flexibility to capture dynamic relationships between people, events, and objects. FRBRoo, an extension of FRBR aligned with CIDOC CRM, bridges the gap between library and cultural heritage models by emphasizing relationships between abstract works, their expressions, and manifestations. This integration facilitates the representation of performances as evolving entities, accounting for multiple iterations and contexts.

Several specialized frameworks have been developed to address specific needs in performing arts data. AusStage (Bollen 2016), a database and ontology tailored for Australian performing arts, builds on CIDOC CRM to represent events, venues, and participants in the context of national and cultural heritage. Its event-centric design aligns with CIDOC CRM principles while addressing specific regional needs. The Europeana Data Model (EDM) also draws from FRBR and CIDOC CRM to support the aggregation of metadata across Europe's cultural institutions. While not explicitly focused on performing arts, its modular approach and alignment with linked open data standards demonstrate its adaptability for capturing complex cultural phenomena. Similarly, the SPA Data Model initiative adapts FRBR to streamline performing arts representation. The *CapData Opéra* ontology (Peyre, Amarger, and Chauvat 2024), developed by the Réunion des Opéras de France (ROF), uses Semantic Web technologies to enhance data interoperability among opera houses. By aligning with schema.org and employing RDF-based structures, it standardizes and validates cultural data, enabling centralized querying via a SPARQL endpoint. This project shares the same philosophy as the Linked Digital Future for the Performing Arts⁶ developed in Canada. Their objective, even if the formalization differs, is similar: to promote the discoverability of works online. These last two models are aimed primarily at cultural institutions.

Challenges in Performing Arts Data Modeling

Some of these models rely on RDF principles. Despite all its promises for the performing arts, relayed in particular in an article by Miguel Escobar Varela (Escobar Varela 2016), the semantic web remains little used in the field, both in terms of repository, structuring and exploitation of data. This is evidenced by the near-absence of the subject in the discipline's major international conferences, such as those organized by the International Federation for Theatre Research (IFTR) and SIBMAS, or in special issues of journals devoted to the performing arts and digital humanities (*Theatre Journal* 2016; Galleron 2017)

By critically engaging with these models on specific examples from the Festival d'Avignon dataset, we highlights persistent gaps and challenges in harmonizing data across institutions. These different models, despite their respective qualities, are often designed for specific archives or datasets. While they allow us to take into account the specific features of the works in these collections, and even specific research questions, they lack genericity and, consequently, interoperability. As a result,

2 <https://github.com/ISE-FIZKarlsruhe/LinkedStageGraph/>

3 <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

4 https://www.bfh.ch/dam/jcr:78a5e853-3c03-4ed8-8e28-86e2791a5829/SPA_Data_Model_v0-51_20170926.pdf

5 <https://www.pinabausch.org/page/about-archives>

6 <https://culturecreates.github.io/artsdata-data-model/>

these models operate in silos, limiting data exchange. That's why we're focusing on an approach that would both propose a generic model and connect existing databases and models.

The STAGE Approach: Extending Linked Art

To address these challenges, the STAGE project adopts Linked Art – an ontology aligned with CIDOC CRM – as the basis for modeling performing arts data. Linked Art⁷ is an open and community-driven ontology designed to facilitate the integration and interoperability of cultural heritage data on the semantic web. Built upon the CIDOC CRM framework, Linked Art provides a flexible, event-based model that aligns with Resource Description Framework (RDF) standards. Its commitment to simplicity and usability provides a powerful common vocabulary that cultural institutions can use to share, query, and connect their datasets across a wide variety of platforms and domains. To date, its primary focus has been the visual arts, encompassing artworks, collections, exhibitions, and associated metadata, such as provenance, creators, and locations.

While Linked Art has demonstrated significant success in addressing the needs of visual arts, it currently lacks dedicated support for performing arts. Our initiative aims to extend Linked Art by developing a dedicated framework for the performing arts. This extension will address missing components, such as representations of rehearsal processes, productions, set designs, and technical roles. By aligning with Linked Art's principles, the extension will ensure compatibility and interoperability while maintaining the simplicity and scalability of the core ontology.

The importance of this development lies in its capacity to unify fragmented datasets across the performing arts domain. Many cultural institutions currently rely on isolated databases with inconsistent structures, which limits their ability to share, reuse, or analyze data comprehensively. Adopting an interoperable ontology will connect these disparate datasets to the semantic web, unlocking new possibilities for cross-domain research and collaboration. Furthermore, aligning this framework with Linked Art fosters deeper integration with other cultural heritage domains, enabling holistic analyses that transcend the traditional boundaries between visual and performing arts.

Using the Festival d'Avignon as a primary case study, the STAGE project demonstrates the potential of linked open data. By extracting and modeling data from theater programs, the project reveals intricate networks of individuals, artistic collaborations, and historical trends. Applying actor-network theory (Latour 2005), the analysis uncovers the dynamic interplay between entities in these datasets, shedding light on the evolution of artistic production and dissemination.

References

- Banu, Georges, and Bruno Tackels, eds. 2005. *Le Cas Avignon 2005*. Paris: L'Entretemps.
- Bardiot, Clarisse. 2021. *Performing Arts and Digital Humanities: From Traces to Data*. Hoboken: ISTE / Wiley.
- Bollen, Jonathan. 2016. 'Data Models for Theatre Research: People, Places, and Performance'. *Theatre Journal* 68 (4): 615–32. <https://doi.org/10.1353/tj.2016.0109>.
- Douguet, Marc, ed. 2024. *Revue d'historiographie du théâtre : La base CESAR, bilan et perspectives*. 9. Paris: Société d'histoire du théâtre. <https://sht.asso.fr/numero/la-base-cesar-bilan-et-perspectives/>.

7 <https://linked.art/>

- Escobar Varela, Miguel Escobar. 2016. 'Interoperable Performance Research: Promises and Perils of the Semantic Web'. *TDR/The Drama Review* 60 (3): 136–47. https://doi.org/10.1162/DRAM_a_00574.
- Galleron, Ioana, ed. 2017. *Revue d'historiographie Du Théâtre. Études Théâtrales et Humanités Numériques*. Vol. 4.
- Latour, Bruno. 2005. *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press.
- Oort, Thunnis van, and Julia Noordegraaf. 2020. 'Structured Data for Performing Arts History: An Introduction to a Special Issue of Data Papers: Arts and Media'. *Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences* 5 (2): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1163/24523666-bja10008>.
- Peyre, E, F Amarger, and N Chauvat. 2024. 'CapData Opéra : Faciliter l'interopérabilité Des Données Des Maisons d'opéra'. In *10 Ème Conférence Nationale Sur Les Applications Pratiques de l'Intelligence Artificielle*, edited by Catherine Roussey and Ghislain Ateazing. Plate-Forme Intelligence Artificielle (PFIA). La Rochelle, France. <https://hal.science/hal-04639095>.
- Roussillon, Marine, and Christophe Schuwey, eds. 2020. *Revue d'historiographie du théâtre : écrire l'histoire des spectacles avec des bases de données*. 5. Paris: Société d'histoire du théâtre. <https://sht.asso.fr/revue/ecrire-lhistoire-des-spectacles-avec-des-bases-de-donnees/>.
- Theatre Journal*. 2016. Vol. 68/4. Johns Hopkins University Press.